

MATATAG IN BASIC EDUCATION: THE PERSPECTIVES OF ELEMENTARY TEACHERS IN THE PROPOSED DECONGESTED CURRICULUM

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Matatag in Basic Education: The Perspectives of Elementary Teachers in the Proposed Decongested Curriculum

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Abstract

The study focused on describing the observable phenomena of perceptions and personal insights of Elementary teachers. Moreover, the aim of the study was to determine the perceptions and insights encountered by Elementary teachers. The study utilized a qualitative research design, specifically phenomenological in design, wherein there were 14 participants who were elementary teachers at Maniki Central SPED Center. Data analysis was conducted through thematic coding of the interview responses, allowing for the extraction of key themes that represented the participants' perceptions and insights. It was found out that in terms of their perceptions, several themes were extracted based on the responses of the informants, such as efficiency and focus in teaching and learning, literacy and numeracy prioritization, inclusive education for all and adaptation to new curriculum. Insights revealed from the responses included reading and numeracy enhancement, instill values education to learners, crucial role of teachers in curriculum implementation, impact of decongested curriculum on educational quality and accessibility and adaptation of new curriculum.

Keywords: *Matatag Curriculum, decongested curriculum, elementary teachers, phenomenology, qualitative research, Philippines*

Introduction

The decongested curriculum is an approach to curriculum design that aims to reduce the amount of content that students are required to learn. This is done by removing or streamlining topics that are deemed to be less important or essential. Decongested curriculum has some potential benefits but it also has potential negative impacts like it can lead to decreased student learning, limited exposure to important subjects and topics, and increased stress and burnout for teachers (Wolf,2022).

In Japan, research has demonstrated that the implementation of a decongested curriculum led to a marked decline in student performance in Mathematics and Science. This approach also resulted in a narrowing of the curriculum, restricting students' exposure to crucial subjects such as the arts, humanities, and social sciences. The findings indicate that the decongested curriculum has adversely affected student achievement, prompting researchers to urge the Japanese government to reconsider and revise this educational strategy to ensure comprehensive and high-quality education for all students (Kiyokawa & Ichikawa,2019).

Similarly, the Philippines is poised to experience potential short-term disruptions with the transition to the Matatag Curriculum. This shift is likely to require updates to teaching materials, the introduction of new assessment methods, and modifications to classroom dynamics. Such changes may lead to temporary confusion among students and educators, potentially impacting the overall quality of education during the transition period (Ocampo, 2023).

This matter is of significant importance, necessitating a study that examines the viewpoints of primary school educators concerning the suggested streamlined curriculum. Currently, this issue persists within both the community and the local context due to the imminent introduction of the new curriculum, directly impacting elementary teachers. There is urgency to conduct this study because it can help the elementary teachers to understand the impact of this curriculum on student learning and to develop recommendations for improvement. This study is socially relevant because it will explore the potential impact of the proposed decongested curriculum on elementary education, as perceived by elementary teachers and it can help to raise awareness of how important the education. By doing a qualitative study in this area, I can find out important things that can benefit the elementary teachers in understanding the strengths and weaknesses of the decongested curriculum, they can make better decisions about how to educate the learners and help our society to move forward.

Consequently, the study of Gokhan Bas and Cihad Senturk (2020) titled "Perceptions of Teachers about the Curriculum: A Metaphor Analysis" that examines teachers' perceptions regarding the concept of curriculum through metaphor analysis. According to the findings of the research, the teachers were seen to produce a total of 48 well-structured metaphors for curriculum concepts, which were then grouped under five conceptual categories as guide, problem, system, complex structure. In addition, the study of Krizhia Magallanes, Jae Young Chung and Sunbok Lee (2022) titled "The Philippine Teachers Concerns on Educational Reform using Concern Based Adoption Model" this study aims to identify the Philippines teachers' concerns in K-12 implementation. The concerns-based adoption model was applied to determine the level of concerns, findings indicate that consequence and collaboration was the teachers' current concern. However, this study will be different because it will focus more on the perspectives of elementary teachers in gaining a deep understanding of the curriculum's goals, objectives, and content. Also, with the full guidance of elementary teachers, learners will develop a deeper understanding of the core concepts of each subject, which is still less explored in the body of knowledge. These premises prompt me to propose this study. Copies of the study will be disseminated to the various research conference and concerned

agencies to facilitate scholarly exchange and utilization of research-based discovery.

Upon the completion of this dissertation, dissemination efforts would be done to encourage the readers and members of the academic community to disseminate further and utilize the findings of this study. A free copy of the study would be given to the schools where this study would be conducted. Further, this dissertation would be presented in various research conferences locally, nationally, and internationally. Furthermore, I would guarantee the publication of this study in a reputable and referred journal to encourage further the dissemination of this dissertation.

Research Questions

This research aimed to find out the perspective of elementary teachers in the proposed decongested curriculum. Therefore, important questions that were tackled were as follows:

1. What are the perceptions of elementary teachers in implementing the proposed decongested curriculum?
2. What are the insights of elementary teachers regarding decongested curriculum?

Methodology

Research Design

This qualitative study adopted phenomenology as its design. Qualitative research served as a method for exploring and understanding the meaning individuals or groups assigned to a social or human experience. This research design began with a conceptual question and a plan to explore this question through participants' experiences, involved gathering data from participants in their environment, inductively analyzing the data, building from specific to general themes, and interpreting the significance of the findings (Creswell, 2018).

In this study, qualitative research was employed to gain an in-depth understanding of elementary teachers' perceptions and recommendations regarding the proposed decongested curriculum. Data were collected through participant interviews, contrasting with a quantitative approach, which would use survey responses and numerical data to address the research question.

Furthermore, the study utilized a qualitative research method known as phenomenology. Phenomenology focused on the shared aspects of individuals' lived experiences. This approach aimed to provide a comprehensive account of consciousness or experiences, considering thoughts, feelings, social interactions, and the nature of the world as perceived. The goal was to describe the essence of the specific phenomenon (Creswell, 2013).

In this context, phenomenology served as a means to understand and communicate the fundamental nature of a phenomenon under investigation. It helped maintain the researchers' assumptions in check while exploring individuals' ordinary experiences. This approach was deemed appropriate for the research, given the need to understand elementary teachers' perceptions of the proposed decongested curriculum.

Participants

The key participants of the planned study were elementary teachers in elementary school at Kapalong, Davao del Norte. Upon participant selection, purposive sampling was employed to ensure that only those who could provide the necessary data were able to participate in the study. The following criteria were strictly adhered to during the recruitment process: (a) each participant must be an elementary teacher; (b) the participants must be teaching in an elementary school within the Municipality of Kapalong; (c) the participants must be five (5) and more years of service; (d) each participant must be handling an advisory section and not a floating teacher; and (e) the participants are willing participate in the study.

Fourteen participants were carefully selected during the recruitment process. The researcher conducted in-depth interviews with all fourteen (14) individuals, engaging in one-on-one or online interviews with each participant. Additionally, the criteria established by the researcher were appropriate for the study. The participants were selected based on the following criteria: they were elementary teachers with a minimum of five (5) years of teaching experience in public school at Davao del Norte. These teachers willingly agreed to participate in the study. As indicated by Boyce and Neale (2006), participants were recruited as informants through personal contact.

According to Patton (2002), informants must feel at ease, therefore the researcher will ask informants when and where they would like to be interviewed so that they feel comfortable discussing their life experiences. The time and location of the meeting will be determined in consultation with the informants. All of this will be done to ensure the high quality of the study's conduct and findings.

Procedure

The data collection method for this study, which spanned from pre-interview through post-interview phases, was conducted in accordance with a written protocol that the researcher followed.

The researcher established interview guide questions, and the panel or validators validated the guide questions. Then, the researcher got a letter of endorsement. The researcher needed to get the Department of Education (DepEd) permission to conduct the study by

utilizing the endorsement letter. After that, the researcher sought permission from the office of the college president of KCAST, asking for a letter to allow the researcher to conduct a face-to-face interview with the public elementary teachers. After clearance, the researcher obtained a letter for the chosen individuals asking for their permission to take part in the study. The researcher provided the chosen participants a consent form to sign if they agreed to take part in the study. The study was carried out by the researcher following the panel's approval letter. The researchers performed an orientation for each participant prior to the interview. The researcher outlined the study's objectives, methodology, and participants' legal rights during the orientation. Additionally, the researcher requested authorization before recording the entire interview. The collected information was typed up by the researcher. The participants validated the transcription of the data. The researcher translated and analyzed the data after the verification. The findings of the data analysis were utilized to form conclusions and offer suggestions.

Data Analysis

The gathered data in my research were presented and examined depending on the research's objectives or goals. This necessitated a thorough examination of the content of the participants' responses in order to arrive at the study's conclusions. As a result, the goal of data analysis was to look for common patterns that could provide insights that could answer the research questions posed in this study.

Moreover, the data collected in the study were systematically organized and stored by the researcher using technical resources. The audio and video recorders were utilized to capture the conversation. Working, organizing, and combining material into manageable pieces; synthesizing; searching for patterns; and discussing what is significant and what is to be learned are all part of qualitative analysis. The researcher conducted a qualitative content analysis to provide a more thorough analysis of the study. Content analysis involved the study of making inferences from a text to other states or qualities of the source using a repeatable and precise procedure. Following the research analysis, all examined information was derived from a genuine source, which is the informants. Thematic analysis was used in this study to analyze the collected and acquired data. During the data gathering phase, the goal was to find any patterns that represent concepts that the participants represent. The information was then be sorted into logical categories that summarize and made sense of the note's manuscript. Thematic analysis is a flexible qualitative analytical method that allows the researcher to derive new ideas and concepts from data.

In addition, thematic analysis was a good approach to research when trying to find out something about people's views, opinions, knowledge, experiences, or values from a set of qualitative data such as interview transcripts, social media profiles, or survey responses. Thematic analysis was adaptable, and what researchers did with the themes once they've been discovered varies depending on the research goals and the analysis process. Many academics utilized theme analysis to come closer to their data and have a better understanding of the content.

Furthermore, I completed the procedures of familiarizing the data, producing initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and identifying themes, and constructing the report. The analytical procedure began with transcription. I separated the data into bits or elements by analyzing it. It was a process in which the researcher attempted to make sense of the data he or she has gathered.

Finally, I listened to the recorded interviews of my participants and transcribed them so that coding the data will be easy afterwards. I reviewed the data multiple times to become comfortable with the responses and to quickly identify the most common responses offered by my respondents. Then, I aggregated the common responses and came up with a few themes, which I filtered down to just a handful. I used data reduction, which entails removing irrelevant data and re-purposing it as useful study material that the readers can grasp. I sorted and organized a large amount of qualitative data so that I can quickly integrate and categorize it. Data display was used to organize data by displaying it in matrices, charts, and graphs that allow the reader to draw their own conclusions.

Ethical Considerations

When acquiring data from individuals, researchers always complied with a set of ethical principles that served as a guide for research designs and processes. Human exploration typically aimed to comprehend real-world events, investigate effective remedies, examine behavior, and improve lives in various ways. When conducting research, ethical standards had to be followed. These elements served to sustain the validity of the research, promote academic or scientific integrity, and safeguard the rights of research participants.

Moreover, Neuman (2006) emphasized that when producing a research paper, the researcher had to consider many ethical concerns, dilemmas, and conflicts that developed throughout the process. Ethics, as well as the moral research technique, determined what was and was not permissible. This included the following components: respect for persons, beneficence, justice, confidentiality, and consent.

Respect for persons refers to the researcher's respect toward the participants as well as their autonomy in deciding whether or not to participate in the study. This means that research becomes ethical when the researcher delivers appropriate information and understanding about the research project to potential participants, and this information leads to the participants' informed consent to participate in the study willingly (Kalu & Bwalya, 2017).

The researcher created an informed consent form for the subjects of this study in advance. The letter provided more information about the study to anyone interested in participating. During the interviews, the researcher also respected the participant's opinions. Prior to earning the subject's respect, the researcher had demonstrated their respect. They considered their own point of view, culture, and way

of life. Participants were always treated with respect since they mattered more than the study. Ahead of the interview, the researcher also asked for consent to record the whole conversation as well as all participant responses. The participant's right to know the study's findings was also be disclosed by the researcher to them.

Beneficence emphasizes that the study was beneficial to those who would participate. It necessitates a dedication to reducing dangers to study participants rather than generating earnings owing to them (Farrugia, 2019).

The community and participants benefited from this study because the result of this study became the basis for improving curriculum guide and academic support to improve students' self-esteem, confidence, and motivation to succeed, and improve the quality of education in the community. Another is that it could also improve academic outcomes and promote equity and access in elementary education, which would help them be equipped in the field of teaching and become effective educators in the community.

The researcher found a safe area where the participants and researchers could have a face-to-face interview to ensure everyone's safety. The interview procedure gave participants the chance to share their stories in a safe environment without worrying about rejection or judgment. After the interview, the data was kept confidential and safe to prevent psychological risks like shame, embarrassment, and other undesirable outcomes. The research ensured that the risk of COVID-19 transmission between the interviewer and participants was prevented by adhering to safety protocols throughout the interview.

Justice relates to the idea that everyone who was involved in this study should be treated fairly. Regardless of age, gender, race, religion, socioeconomic level, or any other criteria, everyone has an equal opportunity to gain from and bear the expense of the research. However, it is the researcher's ethical duty to guarantee that his research does not lead to unfairness or bias at any point in the process, especially when choosing research participants, to ensure that no group is left out (Farrugia, 2019).

The researcher added purposive sampling to fairly select the interview participants and informants using specified inclusion criteria that is fit for the study. To ensure justice, it was ensured that the participants do not spend any money because their contribution to the completion of the research was recognized. As a gesture of appreciation for their efforts in the study, they were also be given tokens.

Confidentiality concerning the research and findings, as well as participant safety, was ensured by keeping their statements confidential through the use of password-protected folders and data storage. The participants' identities were concealed.

I ensured that each participant was identified using discrete coding, based on Republic Act 10173, or the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which specifies that any information that could be used to identify participants by name, gender, ethnicity, or occupation should be appropriately written to protect participant anonymity. As a result, suitable coding and other safeguards were implemented to secure the participants' identities. In addition, none of my research participants were ever obliged to provide their names on any of the study's forms and the name of the participants were replaced by pseudonyms by the researcher. The researcher also conducted a firsthand transcription of the interviews. After the data was been evaluated, all items, including videotapes, encoded transcripts, notes, and others, were stored and were planned to be destroyed three years after the accomplishment of the study.

Consent was also considered in the conduct of the study. The study's conduct took consent into account, making it a priority to respect my respondents if they wanted to be a part of this study. The permission of the participants was asked before recording the interviews, and they were granted written permission to obtain their approval voluntarily. Additionally, the researcher informed the participants that they had the right to ask questions during the interview, rights to refuse to answer sensitive questions during the interview, and rights to leave the interview without explanation, respecting the participants' decision to not finish the interview with the guarantee that their information would be kept private even after the study is completed. The participants were notified of the study's findings and results.

Results and Discussion

This section was divided into four parts. Part one focused on the participants' data, from which qualitative data were collected. Part two covered the data analysis procedures and the steps involved in categorizing the emergent themes from the results of the in-depth interviews. Part three focused on the responses to the interview questions pertaining to each research problem. Lastly, part four provided a summary of the responses.

Participants

The participants of this study were coming from the different grade level of elementary teachers in Maniki Central SPED Center. Fourteen (14) participants in the in-depth interview made up the total number of participants in this study, which was shown in Table 1. All of the fourteen (14) participants were elementary teachers in Maniki Central SPED Center.

In-depth Interview. There were 14 key participants in this study. They were all elementary teachers coming from a different grade level in Maniki Central SPED Center. According to Heaton (2021) methodology, each informant for the in-depth interviews was given a pseudonym during the interview process. The pseudonyms were chosen by the participants themselves, based on their preference and distinctive physical characteristics, as well as their responses and attitudes observed throughout the interview sessions like this, Blaze was the nickname given to the participant for being fiery and passionate. Serenity was named for her calm and composed demeanor.

Willow was chosen for her soothing support. Grace earned her nickname due to her elegance and poise. Harmony for his balanced and unifying presence. Luna was called for her dreamy and introspective nature. Mavis for her bold and adventurous spirit. Ember was named for her creativity and determination. Phoenix for her resilience and transformative qualities. Storm embodied a powerful and dynamic personality. Jagger was known for her edgy and charismatic demeanor. Ace earned his nickname for demonstrating exceptional talent and a drive for challenges. Skye for her sense of wonder and creativity. Ryder for embracing an adventurous, nomadic lifestyle.

The participants were chosen based on their insights and perceptions about the upcoming implementation of Matatag Curriculum in elementary education, they were recognized and chosen according to the criteria of the research study, and their participation was confirmed by their own personal declaration.

The in-depth interviews were done face-to-face at a time that was convenient for each informant. The participants' data was recorded by the researcher using smartphones, which is a crucial step in ensuring the study's validity and reliability.

Table 1. *Participants of the Study*

<i>In-Depth Interview (Pseudonyms)</i>	<i>Assigned Grade Level</i>	<i>Rank</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Gender</i>	<i>Code</i>
Blaze	Grade 6	Master Teacher II	28	Male	IDI-01
Serenity	SPED	Master Teacher III	50	Female	IDI-02
Willow	Grade 3	Master Teacher II	46	Female	IDI-03
Grace	Kinder	Master Teacher III	51	Female	IDI-04
Harmony	Grade 5	Master Teacher II	27	Female	IDI-05
Luna	Grade 3	Master Teacher III	56	Female	IDI-06
Mavis	Grade 5	Teacher III	29	Female	IDI-07
Ember	Grade 1	Master Teacher II	42	Female	IDI-08
Phoenix	Grade 4	Teacher II	38	Female	IDI-09
Storm	Grade 4	Master Teacher I	30	Male	IDI-10
Jagger	Grade 2	Teacher III	28	Female	IDI-11
Ace	Grade 1	Master Teacher II	36	Male	IDI-12
Skye	Grade 2	Teacher III	31	Female	IDI-13
Ryder	Kinder	Master Teacher II	54	Female	IDI-14

Categorization of Data

After the interview, recorded conversations were transcribed, translated, and subsequently analyzed. The researcher initiated the analysis through the process of coding.

Coding is the technique of arranging resources into pieces of text before giving meaning to the information. The coding technique was utilized to provide a description of the set of people as well as the categories of themes to be analyzed. These topics were used to help form a broad description of the phenomena under investigation.

In order to classify the data, the major themes were given in order to address each research question. To give a detailed overview, the study's themes were thoroughly discussed and elaborated to provide a vivid description. Then came the conclusion and verification, where the synthesized insights were compared with existing literature to validate the robustness of the findings (Miles & Huberman, 1994). Finally, the culmination of this process offered a comprehensive understanding of the research's implications within the broader scholarly context.

In order to add trustworthiness to the study, the researcher made note of the dimensions of credibility, dependability, transferability, and confirmability. To address credibility, member verification was carried out in addition to the triangulation approach. This was accomplished by providing copies of the interview transcript to participants so they may remark on it and certify to its authenticity. None of the informants have yet voiced any criticism of the transcript or offered any contradictory information. They all put their signatures on the participant verification form to indicate that they said yes. The triangulation of the study was made possible by the fact that it contained readings from participants and linked works, or more than two sources (Creswell & Miller, 2003).

In order to add trustworthiness to my study, the researcher made note of the dimensions of credibility, dependability, transferability, and confirmability. To address credibility, member verification was carried out in addition to the triangulation approach. This was accomplished by providing copies of the interview transcript to participants so they may remark on it and certify to its authenticity. None of the informants have yet voiced any criticism of the transcript or offered any contradictory information. They all signed the participant's verification form to confirm their affirmative response. The study's triangulation was made possible by the fact that it included more than two sources, specifically, readings from related literature and participants (Creswell & Miller, 2003).

To ensure dependability and confirmability, the researcher provided an audit trail. This trail was established with the purpose of allowing the research review panel to validate the results, assumptions, and conjectures put forth in the study (Carcary, 2009).

In terms of transferability, the researcher stated from the beginning that the results cannot be generalized because these views were based only on the participants' own experiences in the indicated localities. Nonetheless, the researcher agreed that when the credibility,

confirmability, and dependability of a qualitative case study are assured, then transferability is addressed as well (Gempes et al., 2009).

Research Question No. 1: What are the perceptions of elementary teachers in implementing the proposed decongested curriculum?

In the first main question which was about the perceptions of elementary teachers in implementing the proposed decongested curriculum, there are four emerging themes that the researcher had found after thorough analysis considering all the participants' responses. These themes were: efficiency and focus in teaching and learning, literacy and numeracy prioritization, inclusive education for all, and adaptation to new curriculum. Below was the presentation of the emerging themes together with the supporting statements provided by the participants.

Efficiency and Focus in Teaching and Learning

Efficiency and focus in teaching and learning are paramount for elementary teachers tasked with implementing a proposed decongested curriculum. By streamlining content and eliminating unnecessary elements, educators can allocate more time to key concepts, ensuring a deeper understanding among students. The reduced curriculum load allows teachers to employ innovative and student-centered teaching methodologies, fostering engagement and active participation. With a targeted focus on essential skills and knowledge, educators can personalize instruction to meet the diverse needs of their students, promoting a more effective and efficient learning environment. Additionally, the decongested curriculum empowers teachers to provide timely feedback and support, enhancing the overall learning experience and laying a solid foundation for lifelong academic success.

Table 2. *The Perceptions of Elementary Teachers in Implementing the Proposed Decongested Curriculum*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statement</i>
Efficiency and Focus in Teaching and Learning	"More efficient when it comes to children they can concentrate more on the identified competencies. My perception as a teacher is that, aside from the children having a focused approach, we, as teachers, are also given more time to prepare and our discussion on a particular topic can be extended because unnecessary lessons have been eliminated." IDI-01
	"This curriculum was designed to make it easier for teachers and, of course, for the students as well. I am convinced that this new curriculum will help our learners concentrate more on their studies, focusing on what truly matters in the curriculum without it being overwhelming for them." IDI-10
	"It is much easier and attainable, not as challenging to comply with compared to the recent curriculum. The program and the subjects inside more attainable by consolidating them into well-defined and relevant subjects. This approach is easier to comply unlike having numerous subjects that both students and teachers may find difficult to keep up." IDI-14
	"The potential benefits that a decongested curriculum might bring to the teaching and learning process is I expect that its more on benefits of the children also lessen the tasks of the teachers." IDI-04 "I believe that decongesting the curriculum is a great help for us teachers and the learners because there is a specific focus in which we can produce a competent, read, and responsible learners." IDI-02
Literacy and Numeracy Prioritization	"The Matatag Curriculum places a greater emphasis on enhancing the children's values and skills in reading and literacy. We've noticed that there are students who reach grade six without being proficient readers. The curriculum is being changed to allocate more time for developing the necessary knowledge and skills that are crucial for the current level of the students." IDI-07
	"The Matatag Curriculum is to focus more on literacy and numeracy and to produce a competent, responsible and productive learners especially in molding the values formation of the learners." IDI-12
	"The goals and objectives of the decongested curriculum is the reduction of the subjects from kinder to grade 3 to focus on the fundamental skills such as oracy and numeracy and I believe it will also intensify values education and strengthen peace education." IDI-08
	"The Department of Education recently launched the Matatag Curriculum, which aims to decongest the current K-to-12 Curriculum on which it includes a deduction and is more focused on the development of fundamental skills such as literacy, numeracy, and socio-emotional skills for kindergarten to grade 3." IDI-06
Inclusive Education for All	"This curriculum provides the guide for teachers about academic standards to be achieved with no discrimination, no segregation or in general curriculum for all learners." IDI-02
	"I believe that having this curriculum will make things easier for teachers due to the streamlined learning materials. The learning process itself will be more straightforward for both children and teachers. My expectation is that, aside from its ease, no child will be left behind, especially in reading and arithmetic, as these are the focal points of the Matatag Curriculum." IDI-05
	"It is expected that this curriculum provides basic framework and guide for key learning area, it is specific, the boundaries and as well as the destinations that guide teacher and learners about the academic standard to be achieved by our learners, no discriminations, and the development of the whole being of the learners is emphasized." IDI-12
	"No one will be left behind, it's education for all, including those with disabilities, everyone is included." IDI-03 "Regarding Maniki Central, we have Section One for fast learners and the regular section. As what I understand is that with the implementation of the Matatag Curriculum, it seems like there will be no more discrimination among the children. There won't be distinctions like FL and Section 1; it's more of an inclusive education, which is better."

IDI-07

Adaptation to New Curriculum

“Our challenge is how to adapt to the new one, considering that we have been accustomed to the old curriculum for the past five years. Our main challenge lies in shifting to the new curriculum and how to integrate the competencies that were removed.” IDI-01

“Challenges as we say, are learner-centered. So, being a learner-centered teacher, you have to adapt based on the child's capacity but what you really need to do is to align with the curriculum, you need to balance your time, balance your approach, and figure out how to do it.” IDI-03

“Challenges, I think, maybe more on learning materials because they are new so if the Matatag Curriculum will be implemented, it is a burden for the teachers to create these learning materials for the learners. Perhaps, the Department of Education will provide books and time to craft activity sheets and other learning materials.” IDI-05

“Similar to other curricula we have, there are significant challenges because we have a new curriculum, new guides, and new mandates from our department. We can't adapt to it immediately; we will gradually adapt, not abruptly. We will get the new curriculum, this Matatag it might be difficult, but what we teachers should do is embrace the new curriculum because it won't be established without studies.” IDI-12

“It's really a challenge for us because it's a new curriculum, and we need to adapt to new strategies and methods in lesson planning. There were plenty of old curricula we used before, but now it's quite challenging because the references are not provided, the old books we used didn't include some competencies, so it's somewhat difficult.

Hopefully, with this new curriculum, everything is provided to make it easier both teachers and learners.” IDI-13

According to Blaze (pseudonym), he believed the first perception emphasizes the efficiency of focusing on essential competencies for children, eliminating repetitive and non-essential lessons to enhance their concentration. It is noted that he thinks this streamlined approach not only benefits students but also allows educators more time for preparation and facilitates in-depth discussions on specific topics due to the removal of unnecessary lessons. It is also stated that he perceived that the decongested curriculum enhances both student focus and teacher preparation. He stated:

“Perception number one is mas efficient in terms of focus sa mga bata since ang mga competencies kay identified kato lang essential para sa ilaha, akoang perception as a teacher is aside nga nay focus ang mga bata is kami pud mas mahatagan mig more time nga maka prepare aside from that ma extend ang amoang pag discuss sa isa ka topic since naay mga lessons nga unnecessary nga gitanggal na.” (IDI-01)

(Perception number one is more efficient when it comes to children they can concentrate more on the identified competencies. My perception as a teacher is that, aside from the children having a focused approach, we, as teachers, are also given more time to prepare and our discussion on a particular topic can be extended because unnecessary lessons have been eliminated.)

In addition, Storm (pseudonym) stated that his initial thoughts on the proposed implementation of the Matatag Curriculum are positive, believing that it was designed to simplify tasks for teachers and cater to the needs of students. He expressed confidence that the new curriculum will enhance students' focus on relevant studies, emphasizing the importance of avoiding congestion in the curriculum to facilitate effective learning. He sees the Matatag Curriculum as a beneficial initiative for both teachers and students. It was shared that:

“I believe that this curriculum was made para mas mapadali sa mga teachers of course sa mga bata, naniniwala ako na this new curriculum will make our learners more focus on the studies that they should be focus on, also in curriculum to be taught na that's not congested for them.” (IDI-10)

(I believe this curriculum was designed to make it easier for teachers and, of course, for the students as well. I am convinced that this new curriculum will help our learners concentrate more on their studies, focusing on what truly matters in the curriculum without it being overwhelming for them.)

Furthermore, Ryder (pseudonym) stated that she thinks the new Matatag curriculum implementation is seen as much easier and attainable compared to the recent curriculum. She believes that by consolidating and defining relevant subjects, it becomes more manageable for both teachers and students, avoiding the challenge of coping with numerous subjects in a day. She also includes that the focus on an attainable and easy-to-teach curriculum is highlighted, making it simpler for teachers to instruct and for learners to comprehend, ultimately reducing confusion and enhancing the overall learning experience. She said:

“Matatag implementation is much easier, attainable not so difficult to comply compared sa recent curriculum because they find ways and means nga ang program and the subjects inside are attainable, they fuse it into defined a very relevant subjects which is easy to comply rather than having those a plenty of subjects and then hindi naman ma cope up sa mga bata atsaka sa teachers, daghan kaayog subjects lisod kaayo siya i-comply in a day.” (IDI-14)

(Matatag curriculum implementation, it is much easier and attainable, not as challenging to comply with compared to the recent curriculum. They have found ways and means to make the program and the subjects inside it more attainable by consolidating them into well-defined and relevant subjects. This approach is easier to comply with, unlike having numerous subjects that both students and teachers may find difficult to keep up with in a day.)

Also, Grace (pseudonym) anticipates that a decongested curriculum will primarily benefit children, alleviating teachers' heavy

workload and allowing them to focus more on effective teaching. The expectation is that by reducing the overwhelming tasks faced by teachers, the learning experience for both educators and students will be significantly enhanced. She is optimistic that a streamlined curriculum will be mutually advantageous for both children and teachers. She stated that:

“My expectations regarding the potential benefits that a decongested curriculum might bring to the teaching and learning process is I expect that its more on benefits of the children also lessen the tasks of the teachers since there is so many tasks to comply.” (IDI-04)

The statement of Serenity (pseudonym) conveyed the idea that decongesting the curriculum is deemed highly beneficial for both teachers and learners, as it enables a specific focus that facilitates the production of competent and responsible students. The streamlined approach allows educators to concentrate on essential content, promoting the development of ready and competent learners. She emphasizes the positive impact of a decongested curriculum on the teaching and learning process. She stated:

“I think decongesting the curriculum is a great help for us teachers and the learners because there is a specific focus in which we can produce a competent, ready and responsible learner.” (IDI-02)

Literacy and Numeracy Prioritization

Elementary teachers view the proposed decongested curriculum through the lenses of Literacy and Numeracy Prioritization as a welcome shift towards a more focused and effective educational approach. Emphasizing literacy and numeracy skills at the forefront allows educators to dedicate sufficient time and resources to foundational learning, ensuring that students develop strong foundational skills in reading, writing, and mathematics. This prioritization aligns with the understanding that proficiency in these core areas forms the bedrock for academic success across various subjects. Teachers appreciate the potential for a streamlined curriculum to provide them with the flexibility to delve deeper into essential concepts, fostering a more thorough understanding among students. The shift towards a concentrated emphasis on literacy and numeracy is seen as a strategic move to enhance overall educational outcomes by empowering students with fundamental skills crucial for their academic journey.

According to Mavis (pseudonym), she expressed support for the Matatag Curriculum, emphasizing its focus on preparing children for their next career stages and addressing the observed decline in values education. The implementation of the curriculum prioritizes values education while allocating more time to literacy, numeracy, and reading. She believes this shift is essential to ensure that students, even in higher grades, develop necessary skills and knowledge, addressing concerns about some students reaching higher levels without proficiency in basic reading skills. She stated:

“Matatag Curriculum mas gipalapanan nila ang implementation about sa values education and i-focus nila ang literacy, numeracy and reading kasi as we have observed also there are some students nga naabot nalang sila ug grade six or high school dili pa gyud sila hawd magbasa so i-change daw ang curriculum para mahatagan ug mag taas na time tong mga knowledge and skills nga dapat i-develop sa mga bata na ma nurture sila into nga tama gyud kung unsa na sila nga level sa pagka karon.” (IDI-07)

(The Matatag Curriculum places a greater emphasis on enhancing the children's values and skills in reading and literacy. We've noticed that there are students who reach grade six or high school without being proficient readers. So, the curriculum is being changed to allocate more time for developing the necessary knowledge and skills that are crucial for the current level of the students.)

In addition, Ace (pseudonym) said that Matatag Curriculum is positive, emphasizing its focus on enhancing literacy and numeracy skills. The curriculum aims to cultivate competent, responsible, and productive learners, with particular emphasis on shaping the values formation of children. He sees the new curriculum as a valuable initiative to foster well-rounded and skilled individuals. He said:

“The Matatag Curriculum is to focus more on literacy and numeracy and also to produce a competent, responsible and productive learners especially in molding the values formation of the learners.” (IDI-12)

Furthermore, Ember (pseudonym) said that she believes that the decongested curriculum aims to reduce the number of subjects from kindergarten to grade 3, prioritizing fundamental skills like oracy and numeracy. The curriculum seeks to enhance values education and reinforce peace education, incorporating these aspects into various subjects. She thinks the goals involve a focused approach to foundational skills and an integrated emphasis on values and peace education throughout different subjects. She said:

“I think the goals and objectives of the decongested curriculum is the reduction of the subjects from kinder to grade 3 to focus on the fundamental skills such as oracy and numeracy and I believe it will also intensify values education and strengthen peace education.” (IDI-08)

According to Luna (pseudonym), she said that the DEPED has introduced the Matatag Curriculum to address the congestion in the existing Kto12 Curriculum, featuring a reduction in the number of competencies. This new curriculum places a heightened emphasis on the development of fundamental skills, specifically literacy, numeracy, and socio-emotional skills for students from kindergarten to grade 3. She thinks that the goal is to streamline and prioritize essential skills in the early stages of education. Her statement was:

“The DEPED recently launched the Matatag Curriculum which aims to decongest the current K-12 Curriculum on which it includes a deduction in the number of competencies and is more focused on the development of fundamental skills such as literacy, numeracy and socio-emotion skills or kindergarten to grade 3.” (IDI-06)

Inclusive Education for All

Elementary teachers view Inclusive Education for All through the lens of the proposed decongested curriculum as a transformative and positive step towards fostering a more inclusive learning environment. The emphasis on inclusivity in education is seen as an opportunity to cater to the diverse needs of students, including those with special educational requirements. The decongested curriculum allows teachers to adapt their teaching methods to accommodate various learning styles, ensuring that every student can thrive. This approach not only promotes equity but also encourages collaboration and understanding among students with different abilities. Elementary teachers appreciate the shift towards inclusivity, as it aligns with the principles of equal access to education, fostering a more supportive and enriching educational experience for all students.

According to Serenity (pseudonym), the anticipated decongested curriculum is expected to offer a fundamental framework and guidance for key learning areas, outlining learner boundaries and academic standards without discrimination or segregation. It is envisioned as a universal curriculum, providing teachers and students with a clear guide towards academic achievement for all learners. She believed that the emphasis is on inclusivity, fostering an environment free from discrimination and tailored to meet the diverse needs of every student. She stated that:

“Maybe all of us is expecting that this curriculum provides a basic framework and guide for the key learning areas it is specifies the learners or the boundaries as well as the destination as the guide of teachers and learners about academic standards to be achieved with no discrimination, no segregation or in general a curriculum for all learners.” (IDI-02)

In addition, Harmony (pseudonym) said that she believes that the decongested curriculum will make it easier for teachers due to simplified learning materials, making the learning process more accessible for both children and educators. The expectation is that the curriculum, known as Matatag, not only simplifies teaching but ensures that no child is left behind, particularly in the critical areas of reading and arithmetic. The emphasis on ease and inclusivity in these fundamental subjects is seen as a key focus and strength of the Matatag Curriculum. She said that:

“It would be easier for the teachers to have this curriculum because of decongested learning materials and aside sa mas madali siya there were no children left behind especially in reading and arithmetic because this will be the focus of the Matatag Curriculum.” (IDI-05)

(I believe that having this curriculum will make things easier for teachers due to the streamlined learning materials. The learning process itself will be more straightforward for both children and teachers. My expectation is that, aside from its ease, no child will be left behind, especially in reading and arithmetic, as these are the focal points of the Matatag Curriculum.)

Furthermore, Ace (pseudonym) said the anticipated to offer a fundamental framework, the curriculum is expected to guide key learning areas, specifying boundaries and destinations for both teachers and learners to achieve academic standards without discrimination. The emphasis is on the holistic development of learners, focusing on their overall well-being without any form of bias or exclusion. The curriculum aims to provide a comprehensive guide for educators and students, ensuring equal opportunities for all learners. He answered that:

“It is expected that this curriculum provides basic framework and guide key learning areas, it is specific, the boundary and as well as the destinations that guide the teacher and learners about the academic standard to be achieve by our learners, no discriminations and the development of the whole being of the learners is emphasized.” (IDI-12)

In the statement of Willow (pseudonym), it showed that she emphasizes inclusivity in education, asserting that no one, regardless of age or disability, will be left behind.

It underscores the commitment to providing education for all, with a specific mention of inclusivity for individuals with disabilities, emphasizing their equal participation in the educational process. The sentiment strongly promotes an inclusive approach that ensures everyone has the opportunity to access education. She responded that:

“Walang sino man o walang batang maiiwan, education for all, bisan naa pa siyay disability kana tanan, apil jud siya.” (IDI-03)

(No one will be left behind, it's education for all, including those with disabilities, everyone is included.)

Also, the statement of Mavis (pseudonym) mentions Maniki Central's educational structure with fast learners and regular sections. She expresses difficulty in understanding the Matatag Curriculum but highlight its implementation, emphasizing its potential to eliminate discrimination among students, promoting inclusive education, and suggesting overall improvement. She stated that:

“As Maniki Central diba as you have known nga naa miy section one, fast learners and regular section. Ang akoang nahibal-an by that implementation of Matatag Curriciulum ibalik siya nga murag wala nay discrimination sa mga bata wala nay ginatawag nga FL and section 1 kanang inclusive education na jud siya, so mas maayo.” (IDI-07)

(Regarding Maniki Central, as you know, we have Section One for fast learners and the regular section. As what I understand is that with the implementation of the Matatag Curriculum, it seems like there will be no more discrimination among the children. There won't be distinctions like FL (fast learners) and Section 1; it's more of an inclusive education, which is better.)

Adaptation to New Curriculum

Elementary teachers' perceptions of adapting to a new curriculum, particularly the proposed decongested curriculum, reflect a complex mix of challenges and opportunities. Some teachers may embrace the changes as a positive shift, appreciating the streamlined content and potential benefits for student learning. However, others might grapple with the adjustment, facing uncertainties about effective implementation and concerns about adequately covering essential topics. The success of the adaptation hinges on the support provided to teachers, the clarity of curriculum guidelines, and ongoing professional development opportunities to enhance their confidence and effectiveness in delivering the revised curriculum.

The statement of Blaze (pseudonym) emphasized the challenge in adapting to the new curriculum after being accustomed to the old one for the past five years. He believes that the adaptation involves shifting to the new curriculum and addressing the preparation aspect, which is not overly difficult for them. The main challenge lies in integrating the competencies that were removed into the current curriculum, ensuring they are not treated as separate topics but are seamlessly incorporated to maintain their significance for students. He stated that:

“Ang challenge namo is how to adapt the new one nga nasabay mi for the past five years sa daan nga curriculum, so ang pag adapt in terms of pag shift sa curriculum at the same time sa preparation. Ang challenge nalang jud namo is sa mga natanggal nga mga competencies, naa man gud toy mga essential nga natanggal so unsaon namo siya nga ma integrate nalang sa karon nga curriculum.” (IDI-01)

(Our challenge is how to adapt to the new one, considering that we have been accustomed to the old curriculum for the past five years. Our main challenge lies in shifting to the new curriculum and how to integrate the competencies that were removed. We need to figure out how to provide integration for those removed competencies in the current curriculum, ensuring that they are still covered for the students.)

In addition, Willow (pseudonym) said the challenges faced are primarily learner-centered, requiring teachers to adapt their methods based on each child's capacity. She includes that being a learner-centered teacher involves going beyond the child's current capabilities, necessitating a balance between aligning with the curriculum and understanding the individual needs of each student. Despite these challenges, there is a recognition that the optimal balance and approach have not yet been achieved. She stated:

“Challenges kanang mo ingon tag learner centered, so learner centered ang maestra mag agad ra jud kung unsa ang capacity sa bata but ang kinahanglanon jud nimo kay apson ang curriculum and kailangan ka ana ug balance sa oras, balance sa imohang approach ug unsaon nimo.” (IDI-03)

(Challenges as we say, are learner-centered. So, being a learner-centered teacher, you have to adapt based on the child's capacity but what you really need to do is to align with the curriculum, you need to balance your time, balance your approach, and figure out how to do it.)

Furthermore, the statement of Harmony (pseudonym) tells that the primary challenges revolve around the creation of learning materials, particularly due to the novelty of the Matatag Curriculum. Crafting these materials poses a burden for teachers accustomed to using old resources. She hopes that the Department of Education will offer support by providing books and allocating time for teachers to develop activity sheets and other necessary learning materials. She stated:

“Challenges siguro I think more on learning materials lisod magbuhat ug learning materials so if Matatag Curriculum will be implemented it is a burden for the teachers to make this learning materials for the learners, siguro maghatag ang DEPED ug books, time to craft activity sheets and other learning materials.” (IDI-05)

(Challenges, I think, maybe more on learning materials. It's challenging to create learning materials because they are new so if the Matatag Curriculum will be implemented, it is a burden for the teachers to create these learning materials for the learners. Perhaps, the Department of Education will provide books and time to craft activity sheets and other learning materials.)

According to Ace (pseudonym), she said that the implementation of the new Matatag Curriculum presents significant challenges due to its novelty, including new guides and mandates from the department. Adaptation is expected to be gradual rather than abrupt, with a year-by-year approach to incorporating the new curriculum. Although initial difficulties are anticipated, the speaker emphasizes the importance of teachers embracing the changes, emphasizing that the curriculum is based on studies and requires collective efforts for successful implementation. Her statement was:

“The same to other curriculum we have there's a big challenge because we have a new curriculum, new guides, new mandates sa atoang department also hindi natin yan ma a-adapt agad-agad, gradually natin yan na a-adapt hindi yung abrupt, year by year makukuha natin yung new curriculum. This Matatag at first medyo mahirap pero what we the teachers should do is embrace that new curriculum kasi hindi maitatag ang new curriculum kung walang mga studies.” (IDI-12)

(Similar to other curricula we have, there are significant challenges because we have a new curriculum, new guides, and new mandates from our department. We can't adapt to it immediately; we will gradually adapt, not abruptly. We will get the new curriculum, this Matatag it might be difficult, but what we teachers should do is embrace the new curriculum because it won't be established without

studies.)

Also, the statement of Skye (pseudonym) said that adapting to the new curriculum poses a challenge as teachers must incorporate novel strategies and methods into lesson planning. The absence of additional references and books makes it challenging to address gaps in competencies not covered by the old curriculum. She hopes that the new curriculum will streamline resources, providing both teachers and learners with the necessary materials, ultimately reducing challenges. She stated that:

“Ma challenge jud mi ani kay new curriculum man siya mag adapt man mi ug new strategy ug methods, sa lesson planning daghan kaayo ang mga daan nga curriculum ato unya daghan ug changes jud kay mangita pa ug laing references kay dili man provided, katong daan nga books ang ginagamit namo tapos wala didto ang ubang competency. Unta kani nga curriculum dapat kanang provided para dali lang wala kaayoy challenges para sa teachers ug learners.” (IDI-13)

(It's really a challenge for us because it's a new curriculum, and we need to adapt to the new strategies and methods. In lesson planning, there were plenty in the old curricula we used before but it's quite challenging because the references are not provided, the old books we used didn't include some competencies, so it's somewhat difficult. Hopefully, with this new curriculum, everything is provided to make it easier for both teachers and learners.)

Research Question No. 2: What are the insights of elementary teachers regarding decongested curriculum?

In the second question, participants were asked what are their insights regarding decongested curriculum. In the responses of the participants, the researcher identified five themes in the coding process which were: reading and numeracy enhancement, instill values education to learners, crucial role of teachers in curriculum implementation, impact of decongested curriculum on educational quality and accessibility and adaptation of new curriculum.

Table 3. The Insights of Elementary Teachers Regarding Decongested Curriculum

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statement</i>
Reading and Numeracy Enhancement	<p>“The main focus right now is the reading and numeracy because every two years, the PISA conducts international assessments and for consecutive years, the DEPED has participated, it has consistently ranked low in terms of students' mastery. Children may know how to solve problems but struggle to comprehend what they read. So, the current objective of the curriculum is not only to focus on competencies per subject but also on enhancing reading and numeracy skills.” IDI-01</p> <p>“The primary goal is really literacy because our PISA results are very low, especially in Science, English, and Mathematics. That's why this curriculum will be decongested so that teachers can teach better, focusing on subjects that are necessary for the children's literacy, numeracy, and Science since that's our main concern.” IDI-05</p> <p>“As the survey indicated, the reading skills of our children have significantly deteriorated over time. This is the method or approach to uplift our reading ability because, according to the survey, we are consistently at the bottom in reading comprehension, numerical skills, and mathematical operations. That's why it is given focus not only on those aspects but also on our verbal values.” IDI-12</p> <p>“There are conducted studies that find the Matatag curriculum more interesting, achievable, attainable, and enjoyable. They might find this curriculum more appealing as they studied the results of the PISA in the achievement and performance level of children in the current curriculum, our rank is second to last.” IDI-14</p>
Instill Values Education to Learners	<p>“They really want our learners to embrace their values education. As we observe our children now, it seems quite different. Sometimes, they even forget the polite expressions they used to say like "po" and "opo" (yes ma'am/yes sir) and "salamat po" (thank you). In the past, our elders taught us that if you encounter older people at night, you immediately greet them with "good evening" or "good night." That seems to be disappearing now. So, their objective is to equip the children not only academically but also with good moral values.” IDI-07</p> <p>“We will be happy to work with the children, especially strengthening their learning through reading, literacy, and, most importantly, values formation. The values that seem to be fading away, like showing respect when students do "mano" (bless) or when they meet someone, as if they're no longer afraid of teachers. Let's bring back the focus on the whole aspect of the child, especially their behavior, just like in the old days.” IDI-12</p> <p>“This curriculum really focuses on reading with comprehension, and it includes values education. Most children nowadays don't use polite expressions like "po" and "opo." Instead, they might just bump into you without the courtesy, in the past, where there used to be a sense of respect, and children would bow.” IDI-03</p>
Crucial Role of Teachers in Curriculum Implementation	<p>“The role of the teacher in playing in this process of this curriculum development and implementation is she is the moderator, the manager of her classroom, she plays a great role in molding the young minds of our learners so there is a good foundation if the teacher will adapt this Matatag Curriculum.” IDI-04</p> <p>“Teachers plays a vital role in curriculum development, bringing their expertise, experience, and knowledge of their students to shape the curriculum they provide valuable input in identifying learning objectives, selecting content, and designing appropriate instructional strategies for their students.” IDI-06</p> <p>“In the process of implementing this new curriculum, teachers have a substantial role. They facilitate learning and contribute not only to the learners' academic growth but also to the holistic development of the child. Teachers play a crucial role in molding the character of the students, as they spend 6 to 8 hours with them, significantly influencing the learners to become good and productive citizens.” IDI-12</p>

“Teachers are like soldiers on the battlefield; they are the ones in the front lines. In the context of the new curriculum, teachers have a massive role in achieving the goals, vision, and mission of the DEPED Curriculum. Teachers are the basic implementors, the ones in direct contact with the learners, making their role pivotal in the successful implementation of the curriculum.” IDI-14

“The primary role here is for the teacher to comply with the requirements. This is the most important aspect – following the suggested process of this new curriculum to ensure a well-implemented and goal-oriented approach. At first, it might be difficult, but teachers should embrace the new curriculum because it won't be established without studies.”

IDI-09

Impact of
Decongested
Curriculum on
Educational Quality

“The possibility effect of the decongested curriculum to the educational system of our country is, it aims to make things easy, to make things possible to happen and to make an education a simple and attainable with the values focus.” IDI-02

“The potential effect of the decongested curriculum to the educational system of the country will give high sufficient education for the Philippines and to foresee the good graduates a productive one and a competitive student and we can say that here is well-rounded.” IDI-04

“The new curriculum supposed to be a response in learning crisis in the Philippines. The new curriculum where it decongests foundational subjects to allow learners to focus on literacy and numeracy skills.” IDI-06

“The possible effect as for me it will lessen the expenses of the parents and less years to be taken of the students” IDI-08

“If it produces positive outcomes, achieving the mission, vision, and goals of the program through this new curriculum is highly likely – a 100 percent achievement.” IDI-14

Accessibility and
Adaptation of New
Curriculum

“Some competencies that the child can't acquire were missed because they were removed.” IDI-01

“My concern is whether the child can grasp it. If they can't, perhaps the old curriculum was better, with just a few subjects like Science, Math, English, and Filipino. It's like going back and forth; there's only CHAR-ED (Character Education) That's my concern – whether the child will still be able to grasp it. Let's see if, with the decongested curriculum, the child can still shine.” IDI-05

“The educational system in our country, for me, is like a trial and error. They want to follow an educational system from another country. They see that it works in the Philippines, and then, at some point, it seems like they see that it's not good, so they try another curriculum. If they have a curriculum that they think will develop the country, maybe they will focus on

that curriculum for a few years instead of changing it constantly because you can't see the development in just a few months.” IDI-07

“In my opinion, the possible effects are that with fewer subjects, the child's development may not be very holistic. It's like their subjects are limited, and they focus more on those subjects. Also, when it's decongested, until it reaches a higher level of learning for the child, it's limited, and they can't explore other areas that needs to explore. Personally, I prefer K-to-12 because we are globally competitive and globally adapted with K-to-12. It's not just our preference, other countries also have K-to-12 because it is research-based. I don't know, Matatag is okay, but I prefer K-to-12.” IDI-11

We admit that sometimes we follow patterns from other countries. We keep redoing our curriculum. Hopefully, whether we pattern ourselves after another country their educational system, it doesn't matter, as long as it has a great impact, especially on our learners. In this problem we have with our children now who can't read, can't understand numbers, and their values, hopefully, these issues will be addressed in the Matatag Curriculum.” IDI-12

Reading and Numeracy Enhancement

Elementary teachers, when confronted with a decongested curriculum, focus on tailoring reading and numeracy enhancement strategies to foster a more profound understanding among students. With reduced content overload, educators can employ diverse instructional methods, personalized learning approaches, and targeted interventions to address individual needs. This shift allows teachers to dedicate more time to foundational skills, ensuring students grasp fundamental concepts in reading and numeracy. By emphasizing depth among breadth, educators aim to cultivate a strong academic foundation, laying the groundwork for students' sustained success in more advanced topics. This nuanced approach aligns with the broader goal of nurturing critical thinking and comprehensive skill development within a less hurried and more effective learning environment.

The statement of Blaze (pseudonym) primary emphasizes the current curriculum is on reading and numeracy, particularly due to consistently low rankings in international assessment like PISA. The Department of Education has identified challenges in students' reading comprehension, noting that while children may excel in problem-solving, they struggle to fully understand written content. He included that the next curriculum aims to enhance both subjective-specific competencies and over-all reading and numeracy skills to address these identified issues. He stated:

“Sa amoang secretary karon reading and numeracy iyahang focus. Every two years naga conduct ug assessment internationally, ang PISA and for the past two years nga consecutive nga naga participate ang DEPED, kulelat jud in terms of mastery ang bata kay kabalo ang bata mo solve pero dili siya ka comprehend sa problem, so ang objective karon sa curriculum is not to focus only competencies

per subject but also sa reading ug numeracy.” (IDI-01)

(The secretary’s main focus right now is the reading and numeracy because every two years, the PISA (Programmed for International Student Assessment) conducts international assessments and for consecutive years, the Department of Education (DEPED) has participated, unfortunately, it has consistently ranked low in terms of students' mastery. Children may know how to solve problems but struggle to comprehend what they read. So, the current objective of the curriculum is not only to focus on competencies per subject but also on enhancing reading and numeracy skills.

Also, the statement of Harmony (pseudonym) said that the main objective of the curriculum is literacy improvement, driven by consistently low PISA results in Science, English, and Mathematics. To address this, the curriculum is being streamlined to allow teachers to concentrate more effectively on essential subjects crucial for children’s literacy, numeracy, and science education. She believes that the primary concern is to enhance educational outcomes in these key areas by optimizing teaching strategies within a decongested curriculum. She stated that:

“First goals are literacy kay ang atong PISA result is very low especially in Science, English and Mathematic that is why this curriculum will be decongested in order for the teachers to teach better, better subjects nga kinahanglan itudlo para mag focus ang mga bata on literacy, numeracy and Science kay mao manay gamay nato.” (IDI-05)

(The primary goal is really literacy because our PISA results are very low, especially in Science, English, and Mathematics. That's why this curriculum will be decongested so that teachers can teach better, focusing on subjects that are necessary for the children's literacy, numeracy, and Science since that's our main concern.)

In addition, the statement of Ace (pseudonym) highlights a notable decline in reading skills of children over time, prompting the implementation of a method to enhance reading abilities. The focus extends beyond reading comprehension, numerical skills, and mathematical operations, as the survey consistently places the educational outcomes at the bottom. Additionally, there is a deliberate emphasis on verbal cues within the curriculum to address these identified challenges comprehensively. He stated that:

“As the survey said ang reading skills sa atong mga bata na deteriorate na gyud siya pababa ng pababa so mao ni gihimo ang way para ma uplift atong reading ability kay sa survey pinaka kulelat ta, sa reading comprehension, sa pagbasa sa bata, in terms sa numbers, in terms sa mga mathematical operation kulelat kaayo ta so mao ng gihatagan na siyag focus not only kana siya pati na ang verbal values nato.” (IDI-12)

(As the survey indicated, the reading skills of our children have significantly deteriorated over time. This is the method or approach to uplift our reading ability because, according to the survey, we are consistently at the bottom in reading comprehension, numerical skills, and mathematical operations. That's why it is given focus not only on those aspects but also on our verbal values.)

Furthermore, the statement of Ryder (pseudonym) highlighted while awaiting confirmation, there’s anticipation that studies might reveal the Matatag Curriculum as more engaging and enjoyable. This speculation arises from a potential contrast with the current curriculum, where the PISA results indicate a challenging scenario, with the achievement and performance level of children ranking second to last. The upcoming findings may shed light on whether the Matatag Curriculum addresses these challenges and proves more appealing to students. She stated:

“There are studies conducted they find it Matatag more interesting, more achievable, more attainable and more enjoyable. This kind of curriculum as they studied the result of the PISA in the achievement result of performance level sa mga bata on this present curriculum, 2nd to the last ang atong rank.” (IDI-14)

(There are conducted studies that find the Matatag curriculum more interesting, achievable, attainable, and enjoyable. They might find this curriculum more appealing as they studied the results of the PISA in the achievement and performance level of children in the current curriculum, our rank is second to last.)

Instill Values Education to Learners

In the context of a decongested curriculum, elementary teachers recognize the pivotal role of instilling values education in learners. With reduced content overload, educators have the opportunity to integrate moral and ethical principles seamlessly into their teachings. This enables a more comprehensive focus on character development, fostering a holistic approach to education. By emphasizing values alongside academic subjects, teachers aim to cultivate a sense of responsibility, empathy, and integrity in students, contributing to their overall growth and preparing them not just academically, but as ethically grounded individuals in society.

The statement of Mavis (pseudonym) reflects on the concern that current learners may be losing traditional values and expressions like “po”, “opo” and polite greetings. They observe a shift in the behavior of children, noting the disappearance of courteous gestures that taught by elders, such as greeting older people with “good evening” or “goodnight”. The main goal mentioned is not only provide academic education but also to instill strong moral values in the children. She stated that:

“Gusto nila learners will embrace the values education, as what we have observed sa atong mga bata karon lahi ra jud kaayo, usahay gani mawala na tong na learn nila nga po at opo and salamat po or kanang naandan sa atong mga katigulangan sauna nga if naa kay

makita nga mga lolo ug lola nga imong makasugat pag gabie mo ingon dayon ug maayong gabie lo/la, ang ilang objectives ana is to equip ang bata not only sa academic but sa good moral sa bata.” (IDI-07)

(They want our learners to embrace values education, as we observe our children now, it seems quite different. Sometimes, they even forget the polite expressions they used to say like "po" and "opo" and "salamat po". In the past, our elders taught us that if you encounter older people at night, you immediately greet them with "good evening" and that seems to be disappearing now. So, their objective is to equip the children not only academically but also with good moral values.)

Furthermore, the statement of Ace (pseudonym) expresses a willingness to collaborate with children, emphasizing the importance of reinforcing learning through reading, literacy, and values formation. He raised his concern about the diminishing display of traditional values, such as the fading practice of showing respect through gestures like “mano” (blessing) and interactions with teachers. He advocates for a renewed focus on the holistic development of children, emphasizing their behavior reminiscent of olden days. He stated:

“We will be happy getting with the children specially i-strength namo ang learning sa bata thru sa reading, literacy and especially katong values formation sa mga bata nga nawala na karon even though gani kanang pag amin sa mga bata murag wala na kaayo gina practice, ang mga bata dili na mahadlok sa mga teachers so kana ibalik tong unang panahon naa jud siyay focus gyud ang teacher sa whole aspect sa bata especially sa iyahang batasan.” (IDI-12)

(We will be happy to work with the children, especially strengthening their learning through reading, literacy, and, most importantly, values formation. The values that seem to be fading away, like showing respect when students do "mano" (bless) and they're no longer afraid of teachers. Let's bring back the focus on the whole aspect of the child, especially their behavior, just like in the old days.)

In addition, the statement of Willow (pseudonym) highlighted that the curriculum places a strong emphasis on reading comprehension and incorporates values education. She highlights a decline in polite expressions like “po” and “opo” among contemporary children, nothing a lack of courtesy and respect compared to the past when children commonly displayed such manners even bowing in acknowledgement. The implication is that the curriculum aims to address these behavior changes and foster a sense of respect among students. She stated that:

“Kani nga curriculum nag focus ni sa reading with comprehension unya apil nato ang values kay kasagaran sa mga bata baya karon kay di na baya ga ingon ug po ug opo bangaan nalang ka diha, wala na di parehas sauna nga naay magalang bow.” (IDI-03)

(This curriculum really focuses on reading with comprehension, and it includes values education. Most children nowadays don't use polite expressions like "po" and "opo." Instead, they might just bump into you without the courtesy, in the past there used to be a sense of respect, and children would bow.)

Crucial Role of Teachers in Curriculum Implementation

In the context of a decongested curriculum in elementary education, teachers play a pivotal role in successful implementation. With a streamlined curriculum, educators are tasked with not only delivering academic content but also navigating a more focused and efficient learning path. Teachers become instrumental in adapting teaching methods, identifying key concepts, and ensuring depth in understanding, as the reduced content allows for a more profound exploration of topics. Moreover, they serve as facilitators of values and holistic development, bridging the gap between curriculum objectives and real-world application. In the decongested setting, teachers can foster a dynamic and engaging learning environment, tailoring their approach to individual student needs, thereby maximizing the impact of the curriculum on the overall educational experience.

The statement of Grace (pseudonym) highlighted the teacher's role is vital in the development and implementation of the Matatag Curriculum, serving as both moderators and manager of their classroom. They play a significant role in shaping the minds of young learners within this framework. A solid foundation is built when teachers embrace and adapt to the principles of the Matatag Curriculum. She stated that:

“The role of the teachers in playing in this process of this curriculum development and implementation is she is the moderator, the manager of her classroom, she plays a great role in molding the young minds of our learners so there is a good foundation if the teacher will adapt this Matatag Curriculum.” (IDI-04)

In addition, the statement of Luna (pseudonym) recognized that teachers are essential contributors to curriculum development, utilizing their expertise, experience, and understanding of students to shape educational programs. Their valuable input extends to identifying learning objectives, selecting relevant content, and designing suitable instructional strategies tailored to their students' needs. She believes that in this collaborative process, teachers significantly influence the overall effectiveness and relevance of the curriculum. She stated that:

“Teachers plays a vital role in the curriculum development as they bring their expertise, experience, knowledge of their students to shape the curriculum they provide valuable input in identifying learning objectives, selecting content and designing appropriate instructional strategies for their students.” (IDI-06)

Also, the statement of Ace (pseudonym) mentioned that teachers play a substantial role in implementing the new curriculum, facilitating

academic growth, and contributing to the holistic development of students. Their influence extends beyond academics to molding the character of students, with their significant daily interaction, spending 6 to 8 hours with learners. The crucial role of teachers lies in fostering a positive environment that shapes students into good and productive citizens. He stated:

“The teacher has a big role in the process of this new curriculum the teachers facilitate the learning and also not only facilitating the learners but yung pagiging holistic, ilang oras lang sila sa bahay nila but dito 6 to 8 hours mayroong interactions sa teacher and the pupils, kami yung may great roles to change the learners into a good citizen and a productive citizen.” (IDI-12)

(In the process of implementing this new curriculum, teachers have a substantial role. They facilitate learning and contribute not only to the learners' academic growth but also to the holistic development of the child. Teachers play a crucial role in molding the character of the students, as they spend 6 to 8 hours with them, significantly influencing the learners to become good and productive citizens.)

Furthermore, the statement of Ryder (pseudonym) highlighted the teachers are likened to frontline soldiers, playing a crucial role in the implementation of the Matatag Curriculum. Their significant responsibility involves directly translating the goals, vision, and mission of the DEPED Curriculum into action. As the basic implementors in direct contact with learners, teachers' pivotal role is fundamental to the successful execution of the curriculum. She stated that:

“Teachers are kumbaga soldier mao na sila ang pang battle field syempre ang teachers dako kaayo ni siyag role to achieve the goal, the vision, the mission of the program of the DEPED Curriculum kay sila ang sundalo sa panggubatan ba, naa mi sa field kay basic implementor and ang teacher man ang contact sa mga learners.” (IDI-12)

(Teachers are like soldiers on the battlefield; they are the ones in the front lines. In the context of the new curriculum, teachers have a massive role in achieving the goals, vision, and mission of the DEPED Curriculum. Teachers are the basic implementors, the ones in direct contact with the learners, making their role pivotal in the successful implementation of the curriculum.)

In the statement of Phoenix (pseudonym), she mentioned the crucial role for teachers is to ensure compliance with the requirements of the new curriculum, emphasizing the importance of following the suggested processes for a well-implemented and goal-oriented approach. While initially challenging, the speaker advocates for teachers to embrace the new curriculum, highlighting its foundation in research and the need to adapt despite the initial difficulties. She encourages teachers to proactively engage with the curriculum to foster its successful establishment. She responded that:

“Ang pinaka role diri is mutuman si teacher as to what is required sa amoa mao jud na ang pinaka importante, sundon ug unsay proseso aning bag-o nga curriculum nga gi suggest kay aron mapa implement pag-ayo ug unsa ang goals ani nga bag-ong curriculum. Ang una jud ani murag lisod pero amoang himoon kay amoa ning i-embrace kay di mani i-implement kung wala ni gi studyhan.” (IDI-09)

(The primary role here is for the teacher to comply with the requirements. This is the most important aspect following the suggested process of this new curriculum to ensure a well-implemented and goal-oriented approach. At first, it might be difficult but teachers should embrace the new curriculum because it won't be established without studies.)

Impact of Decongested Curriculum on Educational Quality

The impact of a decongested curriculum on educational quality, as perceived by elementary teachers, is significant. With a streamlined approach, teachers find greater flexibility to delve deeper into key concepts, ensuring a more comprehensive understanding among students. The reduced content allows educators to adopt varied and effective teaching strategies, catering to diverse learning styles and individual needs. This streamlined curriculum enables teachers to focus not only on academic aspects but also on fostering critical thinking, creativity, and a holistic development approach, ultimately contributing to an enhanced overall education quality in the elementary level.

The statement of Serenity (pseudonym) conveyed the idea that the decongested curriculum holds the potential to significantly impact the educational system by simplifying education and making it more achievable. The primary goal of this curriculum change is to emphasize values alongside academic content. She emphasized the intended effect is a streamlined and more accessible educational experience with a strong focus on instilling core values. She stated:

“The decongested curriculum aims to make things easy, to make things possible to happen and to make an education a simple and attainable with the values focus.” (IDI-02)

In addition, the statement of Grace (pseudonym) highlighted the decongested curriculum aspires to have a positive impact on the Philippines' educational system by delivering high-quality education. The overarching goal is to produce graduates who possess qualities of productivity, competitiveness, and well-roundedness. The curriculum envisions shaping individuals who are not only academically proficient but also equipped with the skills and attributes essential for success in various aspects of life. She stated:

“The possible effect of the decongested curriculum to the educational system of the country will give high sufficient education for the Philippines and to foresee the good graduates a productive one and a competitive student and we can say that there is well-rounded.” (IDI-04)

Also, the statement of Luna (pseudonym) cited that the new curriculum in the Philippines addresses the learning crisis by redesigning

to alleviate the burden on foundational subjects. This restructuring aims to enable learners to concentrate on enhancing their literacy and numeracy skills. She also emphasized on decongesting curriculum content reflects a strategic response to educational challenges in the country. She stated that:

“The new curriculum is supposed to be a response in learning crisis in the Philippines. The new curriculum where it decongests foundational subjects to allow learners to focus on literacy and numeracy skills.” (IDI-06)

Moreover, the statement of Ember (pseudonym) believed that the potential outcome is a reduction in the financial strain on parents due to a particular measure. She anticipates a shorter duration for students’ education as a result of this measure. Her opinion suggests a dual benefit in terms of financial relief and expedited educational timelines. She stated:

“The possible effect as for me it will lessen the expenses of the parents and less years to be taken of the students.” (IDI-08)

Furthermore, the statement of Ryder (pseudonym) highlighted the likelihood of achieving the program’s mission, vision, and goals is deemed extremely high if the new curriculum yields positive outcomes. She expresses confidence in the effectiveness of the curriculum, suggesting a potential 100 percent success rate in fulfilling the program’s objectives. The statement underscores a strong belief in the transformative impact of the curriculum on achieving desired outcomes. She stated:

“Naa siyay positive output syempre kung unsa tong mission ug vision ug goal nga gusto mahitabo sa program because of this new curriculum, ma achieve gyud 100 percent.” (IDI-12)

(If it produces positive outcomes, achieving the mission, vision, and goals of the program through this new curriculum is highly likely a 100 percent achievement.)

Accessibility and Adaptation of New Curriculum

Elementary teachers view the accessibility and adaptation of the new decongested curriculum as crucial for effective implementation. They emphasize the importance of materials and resources that cater to diverse learning needs, ensuring accessibility for all students. Additionally, these educators highlight the significance of professional development opportunities to aid in adapting teaching methodologies to align with the streamlined curriculum. The insights of elementary teachers underscore the necessity for a well-supported and adaptable approach to maximize the benefits of the decongested curriculum, fostering an inclusive and effective learning environment.

The statement of Blaze (pseudonym) highlighted that the removal of certain competencies from the curriculum has resulted in a missed opportunity for children to acquire essential skills. This absence of specific competencies is seen as a potential negative impact on the overall learning experience. He expresses concern that the omission of these competencies may hinder the child’s comprehensive development. He stated:

“Naay ma missed ang bata nga competencies nga dili niya makuha kay gitanggal.” (IDI-01)

(Some competencies that the child can’t acquire were missed because they were removed.)

Also, the statement of Harmony (pseudonym) expresses concern about the new curriculum’s complexity and questions the child’s ability to comprehend it. Comparatively, she suggests that the previous curriculum, focused on key subjects like Science, Math, English, and Filipino, might have been more effective. The overarching worry is whether the decongested curriculum, which includes only Character Education (CHAR-ED), will allow the child to excel academically. She stated:

“Akoang concern makuha ba kaya sa bata, siguro mas maayo gihapon tong old curriculum sauna nga pila lang ka subjects Science, Math, English ug Filipino mao ra man na, gi balik-balik, naa lay CHAR-ED siguro kana akong concern basin ba ug dili lang gihapon, tan-awon lang nato kung unsa, kung mahimo bang bright ang bata sa decongested curriculum.” (IDI-05)

(My concern is whether the child can grasp it. If they can't, perhaps the old curriculum was better, with just a few subjects like Science, Math, English, and Filipino. It's like going back and forth; there's only CHAR-ED (Character Education) That's my concern – whether the child will still be able to grasp it. Let's see if, with the decongested curriculum, the child can still shine.)

Moreover, the statement of Mavis (pseudonym) perceives the educational system in their country as undergoing a continuous cycle of trial and error. The approach involves adopting educational system from other countries, testing their effectiveness, and subsequently changing curricula when perceived shortcomings arise. She suggests that sustained focus on a curriculum over a longer period may be more conducive, cautioning against frequent changes that may not yield visible progress in a short timeframe. She stated:

“Ang educational system sa atoang country is kumbaga trial and error gusto nila nga naa silay i-follow nga educational system sa lahi nga country tungod kay nakita nila nga maayo i-apply nila sa Philippines then maabot ang time nga murag nakita na nila nga di na pud maayo mag try na pud silag another curriculum, test na pud nila, murag gihimo nilang trial and error ang curriculum so if naa silay gusto nga curriculum nga mag develop jud ang country siguro i-focus nila ang curriculum within pila ka years, dili kay puli-puli kay dili nimo makita ang development sa pila lang ka bulan.” (IDI-07)

(The educational system in our country is like a trial and error. They want to follow an educational system from another country. They

see that it works in the Philippines, and then, at some point, it seems like they see that it's not good, so they try another curriculum. If they have a curriculum that they think will develop the country, maybe they will focus on that curriculum for a few years instead of changing it constantly because you can't see the development in just a few months.)

In addition, the statement of Jagger (pseudonym) expresses concern that a decongested curriculum may limit a child's holistic development by focusing more on a reduced number of subjects. They acknowledge the potential benefits of an improved educational system allowing for better learning and focus. She personally favors the K-to-12 system, citing its global competitiveness and adaptation, emphasizing that is research-based and preferred not only in their country but also in other nations. She stated that:

“Para sa akosa ang possible effects nga gamay lang ug subject kay murag dili kaayo siya holistic develop ang bata kay limit lang man ang subject, hinuon mas focus siya ato nga subject pero pag decongested siya, mag abot ug higher level ang learning sa bata kay limited dili niya ma explore tong other area. Kung ako lang mas prefer nako ang Kto12 kay globally competitive man gud and globally adapted. I don't know, okay man ang Matatag pero mas okay ko sa Kto12.” (IDI-11)

(In my opinion, the possible effects are that with fewer subjects, the child's development may not be very holistic. It's like their subjects are limited, and they focus more on those subjects. Also, when it's decongested, until it reaches a higher level of learning for the child, it's limited, and they can't explore other areas that needs to explore. Personally, I prefer K-to-12 because we are globally competitive and globally adapted with K-to-12. It's not just our preference, other countries also have K-to-12 because it is research-based. I don't know, Matatag is okay, but I prefer K-to-12.)

Furthermore, the statement of Ace (pseudonym) acknowledges a tendency to adopt educational patterns from other countries, using K-to-12 as an example with its additional two years. The focus is on the impact of these adaptations, emphasizing the importance of addressing current issues faced by children, such as difficulties in reading, understanding numbers, and grasping values. He hopes that the Matatag Curriculum will effectively tackle these challenges and make a positive impact on learners. He stated:

“We admit that sometimes ga follow ta ug patterns sa ubang country. Sige rag utro atoang curriculum, ga sundog ta sa ilaha but hopefully kung naga follow ta sa educational system sa laing country makahatag unta ug great impact labi na sa atoang learners, in this problem nga naa sa atoang mga bata karon nga di kabalo mubasa, di kabalo mo kuan ug mga number ug atong values nila hopefully kani nga mga problem ma address sa Matatag Curriculum.” (IDI-12)

(We admit that sometimes we follow patterns from other countries; We keep redoing our curriculum. Hopefully, whether we pattern ourselves after another country their educational system as long as it has a great impact, especially on our learners. In this problem we have with our children now who can't read, can't understand numbers, and their values, hopefully, these issues will be addressed in the Matatag Curriculum.)

Conclusions

The meticulous analysis conducted in this phenomenological study provides invaluable insights into the perceptions and insights of elementary teachers regarding the implementation of the proposed decongested curriculum. The findings highlight the need for targeted actions to address the challenges faced by educators, including the development of professional development programs focused on adaptive teaching strategies and continuous support mechanisms to enhance their resilience and efficacy. Based on the results, it is essential for school administrators to implement regular feedback sessions and collaborative workshops that allow teachers to share best practices and collectively address the curriculum's demands. Additionally, policymakers should consider revising curriculum guidelines to incorporate the practical insights gathered from the participants, ensuring that the curriculum remains flexible and responsive to the needs of both teachers and students.

The study's implications extend to various stakeholders, including educational leaders, curriculum developers, and teacher training institutions. Educational leaders are encouraged to foster a supportive environment that values teachers' input and addresses their concerns about curriculum changes. Curriculum developers should utilize the findings to refine and adapt curriculum content that aligns with the realities of classroom teaching, making it more manageable and impactful. Teacher training institutions are urged to integrate these insights into their training modules, equipping future educators with the skills and mindset needed to navigate evolving educational landscapes. By attributing these actions sequentially to relevant stakeholders, this research not only contributes to the discourse on educational reform but also provides a roadmap for practical, implementable strategies that can improve teaching and learning outcomes. Ultimately, this study underscores the importance of acknowledging teachers' voices in educational change and reinforces the dynamic nature of success, perseverance, and adaptation in the face of curriculum reforms.

Reflecting on the limitations highlighted earlier in this paper, it is worth noting that the study was specifically designed to share perspectives related to the proposed decongested curriculum in elementary education, without claiming to provide a comprehensive representation of all such elementary teachers. Specifically, the research focused on 14 elementary teachers at Maniki Central Elementary School SPED Center. This limitation underscores that our study may not wholly capture the diverse perceptions and insights of other elementary teachers. Therefore, the research topic is ripe for further exploration and validation in future studies.

There is significant room for modification in future research endeavors. Alterations could be made in the research approach, the

participant selection, and the scope of the study to validate and substantiate the findings of this study. The research approach, in particular, could be adapted based on emerging needs or new research questions. Thus, future researchers are encouraged to reproduce, augment, or even challenge this study, applying their discretion and expertise in their approach.

Further studies could also incorporate additional follow-up interviews with the same informants to track any changes in their insights and thoughts over time. This longitudinal approach could provide a dynamic perspective on the elementary teachers and shed light on how their insights evolve as they continue their efforts towards the proposed decongested curriculum.

Lastly, a deeper exploration of the perspectives of elementary teachers in implementing the proposed decongested curriculum could significantly contribute to the research landscape. Such a study would offer educators a platform to share their insights and experiences, providing valuable perspectives on the challenges, successes, and adaptations involved in adopting the new curriculum. By gaining a deeper understanding of teachers' perspectives, we can identify areas for improvement and better support, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness of curriculum implementation and the overall educational experience for students.

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